

**MODERN TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF WORLDWIDE
ISLAMIC BANKING**

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Abstract. Today, Islamic banking is a rapidly growing segment of financial services. This is driven by the increase in the Muslim population worldwide and the penetration of modern technologies into the banking sector. Despite its religious foundations, Islamic banks, like conventional ones, seek to maximize their profits. This article explores the theoretical foundations of Islamic banking, as well as its role and position in the modern world.

Key terms: Islamic banking, mudarabah, musharakah, murabaha, ijara, istisna, qard hasan, salam, Islamic window, Islamic finance, Middle East.

Introduction. Islamic banking is a fast-growing segment of financial services based on the principles of Islamic law, Sharia. The main difference in Islamic finance is related to the perception of the role of money. Money is seen as a medium of exchange, and no interest is charged on it, with risks shared between the parties. The fundamental principle of risk-sharing with clients sets Islamic banking apart, positioning it between traditional banks and venture organizations.

The modern trend in the development of Islamic banking is characterized by increasing demand, geographic expansion, innovation in products and services, integration with global financial markets, and improved standards and regulation.

Islamic banking attracts not only Muslims but also non-Muslims looking for ethical, transparent, and socially responsible financial solutions. Islamic banking is also adapting to digital transformation by using technologies such as blockchain, artificial intelligence, big data, and fintech. It has become one of the most dynamic and promising segments of the global financial system.

The Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB) states that in 2019, the assets of Islamic banks amounted to \$2.2 trillion, accounting for 1.8% of global banking assets. However, the share of Islamic banking is significantly higher in some regions, such as the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), where it reaches 14.9%, as well as in Southeast Asia, where it constitutes 8.9%. Some countries with a significant share of Islamic banking include Iran (100%), Sudan (100%), Qatar (81%), Kuwait (46%), and Malaysia (34%)¹.

Some of the modes of Islamic banking/finance include mudarabah, musharakah, murabaha, ijara, istisna, qard hasan, salam.

Mudarabah (profit-and-loss sharing) is a financing method based on sharing the total profit from an investment project. In this type of contract, the bank, as the capital owner, entrusts its funds to an entrepreneur (mudarib) to implement the investment project.

Musharakah (partnership) involves a joint investment project between the bank and the entrepreneur, with a partnership contract where the parties jointly finance the project. Typically, the entire profit is divided between the parties in pre-agreed shares, and losses are distributed proportionally to the capital contribution. Unlike mudarabah, musharakah allows all parties or one party to manage the investment project.

Murabaha is a contract for the sale of goods between the bank and the buyer at a pre-agreed price. In this case, the bank purchases the goods on its account and sells them to the buyer, earning a profit from the sale. Compared to profit-and-loss sharing

¹ <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/islamskiy-banking-osobennosti-mesto-v-mirovoy-bankovskoy-sisteme-i-problemy-razvitiya>

modes (musharakah and mudarabah), murabaha involves lower risk and is typically short-term.

Salam, or bai' as-salam, is a contract for the sale of goods with deferred delivery against immediate payment and an agreed-upon price for the goods that the seller (the bank) commits to deliver. Salam is essentially an advance form of financing in which one party (the bank) acts as a customer, and the other party acts as a producer (contractor).

Istisna is a banking product designed for financing large-scale and long-term projects. The key difference between an istisna contract and a salam contract is that the supplier of the goods is the bank itself, and payment for the goods is made gradually as the manufacturer produces the goods.

Ijara (leasing) is a contract similar to leasing in the conventional financial system. Under this contract, one party, the bank (lessor), acquires and leases assets to another party (lessee) for a specified period, during which the lessee makes pre-agreed payments to the bank.

Qard hasan (interest-free loan) performs a more religious than economic function in Islamic banking operations. This form of financing can be considered as a form of material assistance on a return basis and can be provided to individuals for various purposes, such as education, marriage, or to enable traders and craftsmen to start their businesses. The interest-free credit system also extends to businesses, with banks providing short-term loans to prevent customers from turning to traditional banks.

The data from Gatehouse Bank's report presents the asset portfolio structure of Islamic banking.

Figure 1. Structure of Islamic Banks' Portfolio

Source: Compiled by the author based on data from

<https://gatehousebank.com/downloads/Gatehouse-Bank-Annual-Report-2021-FINAL-web.pdf>

Islamic banking is significantly oriented towards generating income not from investment activities (musharakah) but from profits from the sale of goods (murabaha). This shift from financing based on equity instruments and profit and loss sharing agreements to debt-based financing denies the advantages of other Islamic financing methods, posing a threat to financial stability and sustainable development. This situation is entirely explainable by the lower level of risk associated with non-investment-related instruments.

At the beginning of 2022, there were approximately 21.5 thousand banks in the world, of which 316 (slightly over 1%) were full-fledged Islamic banks. Additionally, there are 250 Islamic windows² in traditional banks worldwide. The total assets of

² The "Islamic window" is one of the tools of Islamic banking, providing an alternative form of financial services that adhere to the financing principles applied in Southeast Asian and Middle Eastern countries

Islamic banks have shown an average growth of over 15% over the past three years (2016-2021 - 10.1%) and reached 2.8 trillion dollars by the end of 2021, accounting for 2% of the total assets of the global banking sector³.

Reasons for active growth:

- The growth of Islamic banking is continuously linked to the increasing Muslim population in the world, which makes up about 23% of the global population. It is expected to reach 30% by 2050.

- The economies of countries with predominantly Muslim populations have grown by 263% over the past 20 years, with their share in the overall GDP increasing from 3% to 14%⁴.

- The digitization of financial services allows for greater accessibility of Islamic banking services, making them more attractive. There are approximately 375 fintech companies related to Islamic finance worldwide⁵.

- Active support from international organizations and governments stimulates the development of the Islamic financial system through the establishment of the necessary infrastructure, regulatory improvement, tax incentives, and other measures.

Islamic banks operate in more than 40 countries worldwide, including countries with predominantly Muslim populations such as Saudi Arabia, the UAE, Kuwait, Malaysia, Indonesia, Pakistan, and Bangladesh, as well as non-Muslim countries like the UK, the US, Canada, Japan, China, and South Africa. Islamic banks are most active in the Gulf countries, where 8 out of the top 10 largest Islamic banks operate.

The Middle East's Islamic financial market can be segmented by the financial sector (Islamic banking, Islamic insurance "takaful," Islamic bonds "sukuk," other Islamic financial institutions, and Islamic funds), by geography (Saudi Arabia, Qatar, Iraq, Iran, the United Arab Emirates, etc.).

³ https://www.refinitiv.com/content/dam/marketing/en_us/documents/gated/reports/report-2021-all-color2.pdf

⁴ www.pewresearch.org

⁵ <https://www.dinarstandard.com/post/global-islamic-fintech-report-2022>

The popularity of Islamic banking products has surpassed that of traditional banking services in the UAE. While the popularity of Islamic banking among consumers has grown from 47% in 2015 to 60% in 2021, the popularity of traditional banking has trended down during the same period, from 70% to 61%.

According to the 2021 Islamic Banking Index, for the first time since the index was launched, the gap between the penetration of traditional and Islamic banking products in the UAE narrowed to just 1 percentage point, with 61% of surveyed customers stating they have a conventional product compared to 60% with an Islamic product.

Islamic banking has come a long way over the past few decades, evolving into a \$2.4 trillion industry. Islamic finance has become an important element in the development agenda of Middle Eastern countries and is gaining more significance in the region's financial landscape as well as in individual countries.

The demand for Islamic banking is rapidly growing in the Middle East and worldwide, with expectations that this sector will reach \$3.8 trillion by 2024, driven by changing consumer preferences towards social responsibility as a key motivation for using banking and financial products and services⁶.

Uzbekistan's banking practice aims to keep pace with global trends in Islamic banking development. While Uzbekistan has not yet established a regulatory framework for the organization and regulation of Islamic banking, relevant state normative documents are being adopted to stimulate activities in this direction. Independent experts note that the current banking and tax legislation is not adapted to banks operating in accordance with Islamic law, just as the software systems for banks are not adapted. According to experts, Uzbekistan needs changes in the current banking legislation, tax and civil codes to implement Islamic financing products, along with a system for training professionals in this field and increasing financial literacy among the population. Specialists in the field agree that the Islamic finance system will

⁶ www.refinitiv.com/en/islamic-finance.

provide an additional opportunity to stimulate the economy and trade by attracting funds to the real sector of the economy.

According to the Islamic Development Bank's estimates, Islamic banking could attract up to \$10 billion annually in Uzbekistan with the necessary legislative norms in place.

Following the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Further Expand and Deepen Cooperation with the Islamic Development Bank Group and the Arab Coordination Group Funds" dated March 5, 2019, the development of Islamic finance infrastructure in the banking sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan aims to attract consulting support from the Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector.

Furthermore, in the Cabinet of Ministers' resolution "On Measures to Further Develop Cooperation with the Islamic Development Bank Group and the Arab Coordination Group Funds" dated May 23, 2019, special attention was given to expanding cooperation with the Islamic Development Bank Group and the Arab Coordination Group.

In order to implement the aforementioned resolutions, an agreement on "Consultative Assistance" was signed on August 22, 2019, between the private joint-stock bank "Trustbank" and the Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector (ICD). According to this agreement, the introduction of an "Islamic Window" service into the banking system is planned. This, in turn, will serve the financing of small and medium-sized businesses on the principles of cooperation and Sharia.

On January 10 of this year, a ceremony was held to open the Limited Liability Company "Trast Muamalat," a subsidiary leasing company of the private joint-stock bank "Trustbank." It is noted that the primary goal of "Trast Muamalat LLC" is to implement the strategy of expanding financial services within the framework of existing legislation through efficient operations such as "Murabaha (trade with deferred payment)" and "Ijarah (leasing)" and to expand cooperation with international Islamic financial institutions.

List of References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Further Expand and Deepen Partnership with the Islamic Development Bank Group and the Arab Coordination Group Funds" dated March 5, 2019.
2. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers "On Measures to Further Develop Cooperation with the Islamic Development Bank Group and the Arab Coordination Group Funds" dated May 23, 2019.
3. Islamic Financial and Credit Institutions in the Economies of Foreign Countries / R. I. Bekkin, R. R. Vakhitov, G. T. Gafurova, et al., edited by V. G. Timiryasov. Kazan: Publishing House "Poznanie" of the Institute of Economics, Management, and Law, 2011.
4. Biryukov E. New Trends in the Activities of Islamic Banks. World Economy and International Relations. 2008. No. 7.
5. Asni F., & Sulong J. (2018). Hybrid Contracts according to Islamic Perspective. International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences, 8 (5), 453-458.
6. www.refinitiv.com/en/islamic-finance.